

Aspiration pneumonia among enteral fed home care adult patients in Qatar

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Abstract

Introduction: Aspiration Pneumonia is common in older people. Aspiration is preceded by symptoms of dysphagia, difficulty of oral intake, and malnutrition. The use of enteral feeding is the last option for providing nutrition and hydration. 40% of patients receiving enteral nutrition develop aspiration pneumonia with mortality rate of 17-62%.

Methods: Retrospective study method was used to collect information regarding aspiration pneumonia events among all enteral-fed home healthcare patients who met the criteria for inclusion. 276 patients were included after excluding patients who did not meet the criteria. Data collected included: age, sex, time under enteral feeding, mode of enteral feeding (bolus, continuous), route of administration (NGT, PEG), infusion rate feed volume, total calorie per day, total water flushing volume, and total water flushing and feed volume, feed strength and aspiration. Data was collected by three dietitians and checked by the principal investigator.

Results: Incidence rate of aspiration pneumonia during the year 2023 among the study population was 36.96% and mean age was 79.61 years. No significant difference was found between the variables (Sex, age, BMI, route of administration, mode of administration and use of pump). There was a noted decrease in aspiration pneumonia among those who are using pump and those using PEG. When we combined these variables against no pump use and NGT, it was not a statistically significant difference.

A statistically significant difference for aspiration pneumonia was found with less time under enteral feed, and less total water flushing per day (P-Value < 0.05). A statistically significant difference was found with higher calorie intake (P-Value < 0.01). When checked standard adult feeds with other concentrated formulas as a reference group, a significant difference was found between standard formula and 1.5 feed concentration formulas (P- Value < 0.05). All other concentrated formulas have higher aspiration percentages but are not statistically significant. The mean volumes from feed and flushing water were almost the same. The main reason for aspiration is the increased calorie intake through feeds which have higher osmolality or osmolality.

Conclusion: Homecare patients have no active medical issues that require admission; they are considered medically stable. It is important to emphasize the application of safe enteral feeding strategies to individual patient needs.

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Keywords: Aspiration Pneumonia; Enteral feeding; Naso Gastric Tube; Percutaneous Endoscopic Gastrostomy tube

1. Introduction

Aspiration pneumonia (AP) is a pulmonary infection that commonly occurs in geriatric patients [1]. Advanced age is a risk factor for pneumonia and a major cause of mortality in older adults over 70 years of age [2,3], accounting for 75% of pneumonia cases [4,5], 86.7% of which are attributed to Aspiration Pneumonia.

It is noted that patients with AP, particularly the elderly, will usually present with a history of dysphagia, difficulty with oral intake [6] and malnutrition [7].

Atypical presentations of AP include increased respiratory rate, foul-smelling sputum, hemoptysis, and fever [8]. Additionally, Impaired T cell function in older patients may hinder their ability to mount a febrile response [9]. This may lead to many complications which include chemical pneumonitis due to aspiration of acidic gastric contents, secondary bacterial infections following chemical pneumonitis or a primary infection, in addition to acute obstruction of smaller and possibly larger airways through particle-associated aspiration, which is the inhalation of particulate matters of the gastric content [10].

1.1. Risk factors for aspiration pneumonia

1.1.1. Advanced age

Either associated with multiple comorbidities [11] or related to physiological functions impairment [12]. Elderly patients in the community had the prevalence of dysphagia to be 13.8% [13], while in nursing homes the prevalence was 52.7% [14]. General medical literature suggests a prevalence rate in older adults residing in nursing homes between 40% and 60% [15].

1.1.2. Oral hygiene (Oral health)

Half of healthy adults aspirate saliva during sleep [16]. With normal immunity, good cough reflex, normal respiratory ciliary movement, and good oral hygiene, there will be no harmful effects of aspirated saliva. However, with reduced to no activity of the oral cavity along with compromised immunity, the colonization of the micro-flora and gram-negative bacteria are guaranteed. Due to low saliva production in elderly, the chances of bacterial transfer to the lung increases leading to aspiration pneumonia [17]. In contrast, good oral hygiene and the use of dentures [18] were associated with a reduced risk of aspiration pneumonia among elderly inpatients in a community-based integrated care unit [19].

1.1.3. Dysphagia and gag reflux

Stroke, advanced dementia, and Parkinson's disease are the most common causes for oropharyngeal dysphagia in older people [8,20]. Some studies report that abnormal gag reflex and cough reflex are associated with aspiration in the lungs [21]. However, other studies fail to confirm this correlation [22].

1.1.4. Medications

Diuretics, anticholinergics, anxiolytics, antipsychotics, and levodopa reduce salivary flow and increase bacterial flora in the oral cavity, whereas antipsychotics and anxiolytics, lead to impaired swallowing function because of the effect on the central nervous system [23]. Histamine H₂ blockers and PPI increase the pH of the stomach, favoring the growth of bacteria [24]. All can increase the risk of aspiration pneumonia.

1.1.5. Poor nutritional status

Low albumin level [25] and low geriatric nutritional risk index (GNRI) [26] are associated with higher risk of aspiration pneumonia among elderly patients admitted to a long-term care unit.

1.1.6. Use of tube feeding

The risk of AP might increase with the use of tube feeding [27], for several reasons, first by weakening the ability of the lower esophageal sphincter to prevent gastro-esophageal reflux after the NGT placement [28]. Second, the use of tube feeding leads to neglect of oral hygiene practices in patients. Lastly, partial pulling of the NG tube by confused elderly while the feeding is running can cause the feed to drip into the trachea, leading to AP.

Despite the higher risk of aspiration pneumonia with the use of tube feeding compared to oral feeding [28,29]. Patients who fail to meet their nutritional needs orally and are diagnosed with oropharyngeal dysphagia require the use of enteral tube feeding.

The commonly used methods of enteral tube feeding are nasogastric tube (NGT) and percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG) [30]. For elderly patients with oropharyngeal dysphagia, PEG is a better choice than NGT for long term enteral nutrition applications. It was also noted that the risk of pneumonia requiring hospitalization was lower in patients with oropharyngeal dysphagia with PEG [31].

Though results weren't conclusive whether the risk of AP is lower with PEG than NGT [32, 33]. Conversely, PEG use carries many associated problems such as dumping syndrome, dislodgement, and movement of the tube up to stomach, that will limit its use in older patients.

In comparison feeding via percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy with jejunal extension (PEGJ) might decrease the chance of aspiration in the selected high-risk group such as those with severe gastroparesis [34].

No difference was found in mortality rates for patients receiving enteral nutrition feeding infusion at continuous rate (CEF) or intermittent rate (IEF) and pneumonia [35,36]. However, IEF could increase the risk of developing gastrointestinal and pulmonary complications compared to CEF [37,38,39].

Similarly, Head-up positions, such as sitting and standing, and continued oral intake of water jelly administered by a speech pathologist [40] and use of a novel semi-solidifying liquid formula via the nasogastric route are considered effective in preventing aspiration pneumonia [41].

Aspiration pneumonia is the fourth-leading cause of death which resulted in 2.6 million deaths in 2019 [42], and the most common cause of death in patients with enteral tube feeding [43, 44], with Only 38% of nursing home patients were alive at 1 year after feeding tube placement [45]. While the chance of weaning off tube feeding is lower than 20% among all indications for tube placement [46], that warrants more research into this age group.

2. Study methodology

A retrospective method was used to collect information about home healthcare patients with Aspiration pneumonia on enteral feeding using data from medical files at computer-based information system (Cerner) used at Hamad Medical Corporate. Aspiration pneumonia considered in calculation was the hospital admission diagnosis. The total number of patients was 371 adult patients followed by home healthcare dietitians during the year 2023, only 276 patients of which were included after excluding patients who did not meet the inclusion criteria. Data collected included age, sex, time under enteral feeding, mode of enteral feed (bolus, continues), route (NGT, PEG), Infusion rate, feed volume, total calorie per day, total water flushing, feed strength, and aspiration. Data collection was conducted by three researchers and checked by the principal investigator.

2.1. Inclusion Criteria

Adults with enteral feeding under home healthcare department.

2.2. Exclusion Criteria

Adult Patients who were not on enteral feeding, patients with neurological dysphagia like (Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis, Guillain-Barré syndrome, Traumatic Brain Injury, Anoxic Brain Injury), Multiple Sclerosis, Down syndrome, Cerebral Palsy, patients under oral intake with enteral feeding and dead subjects.

3. Results

276 patients met the criteria for inclusion. Data analysis was done by the HMC statistician at ABHATH (research department) using IBM SPSS Statistics version 29.

36.96% of the study population had aspiration pneumonia during the study period (year 2023) and the mean age was 79.61 years. No significant difference was found between the variables (Sex, age, BMI, route of administration, mode of administration, and use of pump), there was a noted decrease in aspiration among those who were using pump or on

PEG, only one researcher who is working as dietitian at home healthcare collected data about the use of a pump; other dietitians could rarely find this information in dietary progress notes, so it was not collected. Results seen in table (1).

Table 1 Chi Square test of significance of variables with aspiration

Variables	# of aspiration/Total Subjects (102/276) 36.96%	P-Value
Sex		
Male	50/130 (38.5%)	0.625
Female	52/146 (35.6%)	
Age		
< 80years	49/135 (36.3%)	0.824
≥80 years	53/141 (37.6%)	
BMI		
<22.5	32/77 (41.6%)	0.504
≥22.5 - <30	52/153 (34.0%)	
≥30	18/46 (39.1%)	
Route		
NGT	81/203 (39.9%)	0.091
PEG	21/73 (28.8%)	
Mode		
Bolus	65/185 (35.1%)	0.371
Continuous	37/91 (40.7%)	
Use pump	9/48 (18.8%)	0.114
No pump	11/32 (34.4%)	
Use Pump and PEG	3/16 (18.8%)	0.107
No Pump and NGT	10/23 (43.5%)	

-Decreased percentage for PEG and patients using pump but not significantly.

We calculated the difference between patients who were using a pump and on PEG with aspiration pneumonia against those who were not using pump and on NGT and found Decreased percentage but not statistically significant difference (P-value 0.107).

Table 2 T-test for significance on variables with aspiration (n=276)

Variables	Number of patients	Mean ± SD	P-value
Age (years)			
No Aspiration	(174 Patient)	78.82 ± (12.171)	0.147
Aspiration	(102 Patient)	80.97 ± (11.339)	
Weight (Kg)			
No Aspiration	(174 Patient)	68.037 ± (14.449)	0.198
Aspiration	(102 Patient)	65.71 ± (14.530)	
Height (cm)			
No Aspiration	(174 Patient)	161.69 ± 8.122	0.893
Aspiration	(102 Patient)	161.82 ± 7.645	
BMI			

No Aspiration Aspiration	(174 Patient) (102 Patient)	25.978 ± 4.94 25.017 ± 4.96	0.120
Time under enteral feed (month) No Aspiration Aspiration	(171 Patient) (102 Patient)	41.26 ± 30.3 32.75 ± 12.517	0.020*
Infusion rate for (continuous feed) (ml) No Aspiration Aspiration	(55 Patient) (36 Patient)	51.02 ± 11.259 50.06 ± 12.517	0.704
Total Calorie No Aspiration Aspiration	(174 Patient) (102 Patient)	1320.98 ± 242.96 1409.36 ± 242.61	0.004**
Feed volume (ml) Q 4 hours No Aspiration Aspiration	(174 Patient) (102 Patient)	218.74 ± 71.81 219.56 ± 39.26	0.915
Total volume from feed /day (ml) No Aspiration Aspiration	(174 Patient) (102 Patient)	1073.45 ± 207.435 1105.05 ± 197.437	0.208
Total water flushing/day(ml) No Aspiration Aspiration	(174 Patient) (102 Patient)	990.832 ± 311.76 914.069 ± 308.42	0.048*
Feed and water flushing volume Q4 hours (ml) No Aspiration Aspiration	(174 Patient) (102 Patient)	412.74 ± 74.73 403.14 ± 72.20	0.298

* (P-Value 0.05). ** (P-Value 0.01).

Results from t-test for equality of means showed more aspiration with higher age, decreased weight, decreased BMI, and higher volume from feed, but were not statistically significant.

Height, infusion rate for continuous feed, feed volume, and feed volume together with water flushing volume showed no difference.

A statistically significant difference for aspiration was found with less time under enteral feed, and less total water flushing per day (P-Value 0.05). A statistically significant difference was found with higher calorie intake (P-Value 0.01).

We also checked if there is a difference in calorie intake between different routes of entry (NGT vs. PEG) or mode (bolus vs. continuous) with P-values: (0.462 and 0.786) respectively, which were not statistically significant.

Association between type of feed and aspiration was checked and great variation from standard feeding with higher feed concentration was found as seen in graph (1).

Figure 1 Association between types of feed and Aspiration

Statistical difference was checked between standard adult formula as a reference with other feed strength using 2*2 contingency tables, and the only significant difference was found in those who were receiving formula with 1.5 (strength), (P-value < 0.05). Results seen in table (3).

Table 3 Feed strength and aspiration

Feed strength	# and % of patients Under the feed	# and % of patients who had aspiration	P- Value between standard 1.0 and other formulas
1.0	72 (26.1%)	21 (29.2%)	reference
1.2	66 (23.9%)	24 (36.4%)	0.368
1.25	8 (2.9%)	5 (62.5%)	0.06
1.28	53 (19.2%)	16 (30.2%)	0.88
1.5	57 (20.7%)	(49.1%)	0.020*
1.8	19 (6.9%)	8 (42.1%)	0.28
2.4	1 (0.4%)	0 (0.0%)	-

Overall P-value (Linear by Linear Chi-Square) is 0.094. * Significant difference, P-value < 0.05. Each feed strength was compared using (2*2 contingency table) feed strength 1.0 (standard feed) as a reference group.

Total volumes from feed and water flushing for different formula concentrations were also checked and were nearly the same as seen in graph (2)

Figure 2 Mean volume of feed and water flushing across feed types among Elderly

Figure 3 Box Plot Chart shows total volume of feed and water flushing with mean, median, upper limit, lower limit, range, and extreme values

Abbreviations and Acronyms

AP (Aspiration Pneumonia), NGT (Naso Gastric Tube), PEG (Percutaneous Endoscopic Gastrostomy tube), GNRI (Geriatric Nutritional Risk Index), PEGJ (Percutaneous Endoscopic Gastrostomy with Jejunal extension), CEF (Continuous Enteral Feeding), IEF (Intermittent Enteral Feeding).

4. Conclusion

Homecare patients have no active medical issues that require admission; they are considered medically stable. In relation to aspiration pneumonia, there was no significant difference in incidence between patients on NGT or PEG despite it being lower in PEG, and no significant difference between bolus from continuous mode of feed even though it was less in bolus. In addition, the incidence of aspiration pneumonia was less with those who were using pump but not statistically significant. Even when gathering more than one variable together to observe a cumulative effect, there was no significant difference (PEG with bolus Vs. NGT with continuous feed), (Use pump with PEG Vs. no pump with NGT). Decreased volume of flushing water and less time under enteral feeding plays a role in increasing aspiration pneumonia (P-value <0.05), but the total calorie intake had the highest effect (P-value <0.01). aspiration pneumonia was found to be unrelated to route of entry (NGT Vs. PEG), nor to Mode (bolus Vs. continuous). The total amount of fluids taken (feed and flushing water) had no effect on aspiration when gathered. Thus, the major effect was something different and when checking the feed type there was a large discrepancy between different feed strength and percentages of aspiration. After conducting statistical analysis to compare standard adult feed (lowest in aspiration percentage) with other feeds, there was a statistically significant difference with 1.5 feed strength formulas as seen in table 3. Highest percentage of aspiration pneumonia in 1.25 strength formula (62.5%).

Higher feed concentration will result in higher (Osmolality, mOsm/kg H₂O, osmolarity mOsmol/l), thus decreased gastric emptying [47]. We can attribute the increase in aspiration to this basic piece of knowledge.

Finally, it is important to emphasize the application of safe enteral feeding strategies to meet individual patient needs [48].

Limitations

- We have seven types of standard formulas including diabetic, two formulas with strength 1.2, one formula with 1.25 strength, two formulas with 1.28 strength, three formulas with 1.5 strength including two diabetics, and two 1.8 feed strength and one 2.4 dietary supplement used as feed for one patient.
- No statistical analysis was done to compare different formulas used with the same strength or concentration.
- Only one researcher collected data about pump use from the three researchers. Completed data about pump use may bring into attention the importance of pump use in decreasing aspiration pneumonia, even if other clinical studies cannot find any differences in Aspiration Pneumonia between patients receiving continuous pump feeding and those receiving intermittent feeding [35].
- Less time under enteral feeding increases aspiration pneumonia; this may be attributed to the fact that care givers had better training in oral hygiene care and self-feeding practices over time and this reduce the incidence of aspiration pneumonia [49,50].
- NGT is recommended for temporary enteral nutrition lasting less than 4 weeks, whereas PEG is recommended for cases longer than 4 weeks [51,52,53,54]. Even with long standing enteral fed patients, only 73 patients inserted PEG from 276 patients (26.45%).
- Data available at computer-based system (Cerner) are available only after the year 2016. Some patients started enteral feeding before 2016 but were only registered from that date. So, the average time under enteral feeding (38.08 months) could be higher.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

Statement of ethical approval

The study design and operationalization adhered to the principles of respect, justice and confidentiality stipulated in the 2013 Declaration of Helsinki Good Clinical Practice. Also, in line with the laws and regulations of the Ministry of Public Health in Qatar, the study protocol was approved by HMC's Medical Research Center (MRC).

Statement of informed consent

Data collected from medical files at computer-based information system (Cerner) used at Hamad Medical Corporate, so no informed consent was collected.

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